

NeurotechBSB: combining academia and industry to improve Biomedical Engineering and Science education

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Abstract— This project is intended to disseminate a proposal regarding the combination of both the academic and industry environments to promote advances in the field of Biomedical Engineering. The aim of this article is to present an approach that can not only improve the formal education of a biomedical engineer, but can help diminish the gap between formal education and industry and incentivize the Industry 4.0 sector. The project is intended to involve both academic students as well as the external community who have affinity with the field; the proposal is part of the North American company NeurotechX and such project will be an arm of the activities promoted by this company, but in Brazilian territory. We plan to promote events of national and international scope, as well as promote workshops and hands-on projects to generate products and disseminate the knowledge of topics such as: brain-machine interfaces (BCI), neurostimulation, neuromodulation, machine learning and artificial intelligence or other implementations related to biomedical data analysis, electronics, robotics, etc. This proposal is hoped to serve as future inspiration regarding educational methods that can be used to optimize both learning and working opportunities for students at many levels.

Keywords — *Neurotechnology; Science education.*

I. Introduction

The biomedical engineering term is derived from the idea that this field is a type of engineering with medical and biological focus [4]. It is easy to see that there would be a complex field of study, since its professionals would have to be properly trained in both biology and engineering - and, within bachelor's degrees constraints, University's worldwide have difficulties implementing an universal basic curriculum for this profession.

In 1998, a center led by the National Science Foundation established a number of issues regarding the formal education in this field: they pointed out difficulties such as dealing with basic curriculum, dealing with special issues (like bioethics and regulatory environments), managing degree's time constraints and dealing with a rapidly evolving field [2]. Unfortunately, ever since then, these problems haven't seemed to be resolved in completion.

Another point of focus is the fact that this field has many

sub-specialties and those seem to not overlap entirely with each other. A special focus of this topic is the field of Neurotechnology: it's a combination of Neuroscience and STEM and involves technical domains ranging from electronics, computation, data analysis and robotics to physiology, physical sciences and medicine. So, the education of Biomedical Engineers with a neurotechnology focus is a special case to point out the difficulties for integrating all of these technical areas into an educational curriculum.

Moreover, the Biomedical Engineering field - and, specifically the Neurotechnology field - has been rapidly expanding in recent years with the creation of neurotech-based companies that are applying advanced academic knowledge in the Health Tech sector - and, especially the field of brain-machine interfaces has gained notable attention after advances by companies that propose solutions ranging from patient and recovery-focused solutions (such as the development of prostheses, implementations with electrical stimulation devices, proposals of equipment for monitoring physiological functions, etc) and for recreational purposes (such as devices based on capturing biological signals for controlling equipment and game applications). With that rapid growth, though, these companies are having to call for professionals of adjacent fields (such as software engineering, psychology or neuroscience) to fill the roles that, in theory, a Biomedical Engineer would have the expertise to fill.

So, this project proposes to present a strategy of combining the biomedical engineering academic environment with a specialized company of this sector to help close this gap and bring to the attention of undergraduate and graduate students the most recent industry-focused neurotechnology implementations - and, for the purpose of this proposal, we hope to bring the Brazilian community in this dynamic and allow the development of this field in Brazil.

II. Methodology and proposal

This proposal is based on the constructivist learning approach, since the student is still the main responsible for constructing their knowledge and understanding [1][3], but can count on both the Industry and the University as support for student learning.

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As a strategy for the development of technical skills and understanding of advanced concepts of the field, several practical activities will be offered to both the academic and external community. These activities will be focused on implementations of programming and data analysis, applications of biomedical instrumentation and electronics, development of prototypes and promotion of international and national events (virtually and/or face-to-face) such as hackathons and technology-focused marathons.

We believe that this proposal will work on two main fronts: promotion of the Biomedical Engineering (and specially the Neurotechnology) field with graduates and undergraduates of adjacent disciplines and allowing aspiring nanotechnologists/neuroengineers to develop the skill-set to apply for industry-related positions. The first front is going to be the main focus of the courses and workshops; since we believe that practical learning activities complement the learning process and builds the actively searching attitude that students need in order to resolve the problems that are presented to them. The second front will be the focus of practical projects (since the main need of this type of professional is to present portfolios and practical projects) and event-promotion (focused on developing networking and communities).

III. Objectives

The main proposals of this project are described as follows:

1. Promote the field of Neurotechnology and Biomedical Engineering in Brazil;
2. Promote national and international cooperation in the field;
3. Professionally develop the internal and external community through courses focused on the areas of interest of the proposal;
4. Develop projects in national and international cooperation aimed at the areas of interest to the proposal.

IV. Next steps

In the first year there will be an inaugural event for the project and as well as the assembly of local groups to host the International NeurotechX Hackathon in person - this event is promoted independently by the company NeurotechX that normally takes place in a virtual format, but Chapters worldwide can create a face-to-face hub to allow the development and monitoring of projects by local teams.

From the first year onwards, at least one national or international event will be promoted (with a minimum of 30 participants, which can be face-to-face or virtual). During the entire operation of the project, weekly/monthly meetings will be held to develop joint projects and/or conduct classes/tutorials for the community.

V. Expected results

We hope to develop projects in the area that will be set up as community-based and that will promote corporations

and advance the field nationally. The results of this project can be scientific products (publications and patents, for example), the generation of events and/or creation/strength of scientific cooperation.

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